

PROFESSIONAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTRUCTORS ON THE BASE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Valiyeva Khamida Ravshan kizi

Assistant-teacher, Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Director of Preschool Education Organizations, Independent Researcher of the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Specialists

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Abstract. *There are highlighted structural organization of selection of talented sportsmen among youth as well as further development of physical education and mass sports, comprehensive study of children's health during the activities of physical education instructors, study of its dynamics, treating of physical and mental health of children, pedagogical technologies used by instructors during the training to form appropriate ideas about a healthy lifestyle in students and methods of their effective use during the training in this article.*

Keywords: *innovation, pedagogical technologies, healthy lifestyle, gross motor skills, fine motor skills, physical development, sensorimotor skills.*

Introduction. To form a healthy lifestyle in our society, to create conditions for the population, especially the young generation, to regularly engage in physical education and mass sports, to strengthen the confidence of young people in their will, strength and capabilities through sports competitions, courage and The order of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 No. Resolution "On further development of physical education and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" Presidential Decree No. 5924 dated January 24, 2020, Youth Pre-school education in order to ensure the implementation of the second initiative aimed at improving the morale and meaningful organization of their free time - physical training of young people, creating the necessary conditions for them to demonstrate their abilities in the field of sports and information on the work carried out in general education schools, as well as the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preschool Education and Training" adopted in 2019 and the preschool education and the main principles of education and the main directions of the state policy in preschool education are explained. It is in order to ensure the implementation of this law that the "First Step" educational program was developed.

Preschool education is a rapidly developing field of education, which is the focus of attention of educational experts and researchers in the whole world and in our country. At present, fundamental reform of the preschool education system is being carried out in Uzbekistan. The state curriculum is aimed at the formation of a child as a well-rounded person and is a basic document that defines the goals, tasks, principles, expected results, content and organization of the education and upbringing process. This document is also the basis for the development of alternative, partial, adapted programs of preschool education.

Interdependent improvement of competences in the areas of development, ensuring comprehensive development of the child, as well as his smooth transition to the next stage, which is school education, and his readiness for it, primary education it is necessary for the formation of

competencies in lim. One of the child's competencies: - physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Physical education in kindergarten is an important part of the educational process, which helps children develop physical fitness, coordination, endurance and strength. Sports activities are conducted in the form of games for children to learn interesting and new skills.

During physical activity, the metabolism accelerates, which helps the active burning of fat cells.

Sport improves the immune system and helps to resist seasonal colds and viral infections.

Regular physical exercise helps to strengthen the spine, which contributes to a healthy state and has a positive effect on the work of internal organs.

Sport helps to strengthen the condition of the cardiovascular system (if, of course, the child does not have medical contraindications for performing a standard set of exercises).

The effect of sports exercises is strong bones and improves oxygen exchange in the body.

Exercise increases cellular metabolism and improves lipid metabolism.

Proper physical activity can help you calm down in stressful situations, improve sleep, and help you focus on important academic tasks during the day.

Goals and objectives of physical education in kindergarten:

development of children's physical qualities and strengthening of health;

formation of the right posture and improvement of coordination of actions;

- development of interest in physical education and sports;
- teaching basic motor skills and exercises;
- prevention of musculoskeletal system and cardiovascular system diseases;
- development of communication skills and ability to work in a team;
- inculcate respect for safety rules in the classroom and in everyday life.

The field of "Physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle" is divided into the following sub-fields:

- large motor skills;
- fine motor skills;
- sensorimotorics;
- healthy lifestyle and safety.

While considering the above areas, we need to set age requirements for children.

The duration of exercises may vary depending on the age of the child:

1-2 years - no more than five to eight minutes;

3-4 years - 10-15 minutes;

5-6 years - 15-20 minutes.

The main thing during the heat is to make sure that the children are not overworked or tired. And before physical activity, warming up is important. It is best to do this in the following format:

walking in place or around the hall;

jogging in place or around the hall;

shaking hands and feet.

Running and jumping are great aerobic exercise options for kids. Such physical activity helps strengthen leg muscles and increase cardiovascular endurance. These exercises can be performed both at home and on the playground near the kindergarten - they do not require

additional equipment. You can run indoor wall-to-wall at an easy pace or compete in a 60-meter relay race.

Walking on hands and all fours strengthens arms, back and core muscles. Crawling on all fours is a simple and safe exercise for all ages that works most muscles. It's even more beneficial to walk on your hands, which develops complex coordination and engages the underdeveloped muscles of the arms, back and core.

Throwing a ball develops arm and chest muscles. It improves intermuscular coordination, reaction and spatial orientation. Children can throw the ball to each other, roll it on the ground, throw it behind their backs, and crouch while throwing the ball. You can also throw balls of different sizes into a basket or target and compete for distance and accuracy. For senior and preparatory groups, you can use balls weighing from 0.5 to 2 kg.

Dance and music classes can also be great aerobic exercise for kids. They are not only fun and exciting, but also help improve coordination, balance and rhythm. These activities can be included in the schedule or used on their own during a game or walk.

Morning exercises

Morning exercises are a set of exercises performed before breakfast. It helps children wake up, recharge their batteries for the day and get ready for active activities.

What does morning exercise consist of? heating up; warming;

A set of basic exercises;

The final stage.

The morning gymnastics complex includes several types of exercises:

warming up - running in place, shaking arms and legs;

stretching - bending, twisting, stretching for arm, leg and back muscles;

jumping in place or jumping rope;

running in place or in a circle;

breathing exercises - inhale and exhale deeply to improve blood circulation and saturate the body with oxygen.

The order of development of fields in children at the age of 0-7 years:

Gross motor skills: The child controls his body and its parts, moves purposefully

Fine motor skills: the child coordinates and uses his hands and fingers for various purposes

Sensorimotor: The child is able to control his movements with the help of his senses

Healthy lifestyle and safety: The child demonstrate health skills, has an understanding of safe healthy food and life rules.

During this period, in order to adapt children to a healthy lifestyle and subsequent educational processes, it will be possible to expect the development of competencies in the field of "Physical development and healthy lifestyle formation":

After the completion of educational activities in the field of "Physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle", a 6-7-year-old child:

shows physical activity in accordance with the standards of physical development related to his capabilities and age;

knows how to perform various mobility activities harmoniously and purposefully;

uses fine motor skills in various life and educational situations;

controls his actions with the help of emotional and sensory organs;

uses personal hygiene skills;

knows the basics of a healthy lifestyle and diet;

complies with the rules of the basics of safe life activity.

Based on these documents and requirements, we can use innovative technologies that we can use during physical guidance activities:

As a priority during the activity of physical education instructors, comprehensive study of children's health, study of its dynamics, correction of physical and mental health of children, appropriate ideas about healthy lifestyle in students we need to consider formation as a priority.

Pedagogical technologies used by instructors during training include:

Development of pedagogical technologies aimed at revealing the child's movement skills and abilities, encouraging children to engage in independent movement activities related to their needs;

Game technologies. The use of well-formed skills and tools, especially the game, allows to understand the tasks that arise in unexpected situations during the activity. Movement skills formed in children under the age of seven are the basis for their further improvement at school, help to master more complex movements and allow to achieve high results in sports in the future. When working with children, we can include:

- games and exercises that develop the ability to identify the main, characteristic features of objects and compare them;

- games that develop self-control, speed of reaction to words, phonemic hearing, intelligence.

Here are some games that can have a positive effect on the mood of children:

"Reaching the sun" Starting position: the child stands, legs slightly apart, arms along the body. Exhale, raise your arms up and stand on your tiptoes. We exhale and lower our hands, return to full legs.

"Let's say hello to the toes" Starting position: standing, feet shoulder-width apart, arms out to the sides. The child exhales and bends on his toes, trying to lower his hands as much as possible.

"Mill" Starting position: legs are shoulder-width apart, the child leans forward, arms spread out to the sides. One hand reaches down, and the other rises, inhales and exhales.

"Applause" The boy walks around the hall, clapping his hands wider than usual to strengthen the shoulder girdle. He alternately claps in front, over his head and behind.

- Watching animals during training, traveling with fairy-tale characters, imitating Olympic champions, playing games and enjoying activities, preschool education. With the help of the above activities, children will acquire the habit of a healthy lifestyle and acquire basic cognitive skills:

1. predicting the consequences of an action or event;

2. check the errors and shortcomings in their actions;

3. management of own activities;

4. to understand the real situation.

- health-saving technologies aimed at strengthening the child's physical development and health: development of his physical qualities, formation of motor activity and physical culture of preschool children, formation of motor activity and physical culture of preschool children, exercise, breathing exercises, massage and self-massage, guidance on prevention of flat feet and proper body posture, fitness exercises on gymnasiums, formation of daily physical activity and habituation skills for maintaining health to give

- **Technologies of social and personal development** - development of mental and social health of preschool children;

- **Art - technologies**, including the use of various methods and tools of art.

- **Problem-based educational technologies**, as we explain the problem by proposing a plot (situation), during which children develop the skills to solve problems in their own world. The child learns different types of activities aimed at learning to solve problems.

Technology of working environment with subjects

The environment in the gymnasium and sports field is created and improved taking into account the requirements of the Program used in the preschool educational institution and the mental characteristics of children.

Students have the opportunity to be organized and act independently, which leads to a variety of physical activities.

Moving through the "zoned" space, the child learns to coordinate his movements and control his body.

The use of these technologies in the educational process helps to ensure the child's emotional comfort and positive psychological well-being in the process of communicating with peers and adults in kindergarten and in the family, as well as the social and emotional well-being of the environment in the world around him.

These technologies help children develop communication skills, develop research skills, and also form the ability to make optimal decisions in the current situation.

The use of computer presentations of educational portals in the organization of educational activities with children on certain topics ("Winter and summer sports", "Sports equipment for sports") can certainly be an auxiliary tool of every guide.

The use of the above-mentioned pedagogical technologies on an integrated basis and the implementation of modern requirements for the organization of the educational process in physical education and health care work with preschool children can help us to come to the following conclusions:

1. to increase the quality of pedagogical influence on children through the development of a comprehensive system of universally integrated knowledge, skills and qualifications;
2. coordination of functional disorders in physical development, revealing preserved opportunities and individual abilities;
3. encouraging children to use the knowledge and skills acquired in independent movement activities related to their need for movement;
4. load optimization taking into account the individual, psychological and age characteristics of preschool children.

Technologies of preschool education are designed to combine all methods into one whole, ensuring comprehensive and effective educational process. It is the formation of the above skills and the use of these technologies in the activities of physical guides that can help preschool children in the formation of the qualities they need to get used to a new environment.

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